

Polarographic Study of Mixed Ligand Complexes : Cadmium(II)-Oxalate-Thiocyanate System

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Cadmium(II)-oxalate-thiocyanate mixed system has been studied polarographically in aqueous medium at 1.0M(KNO_3) ionic strength and at $25^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$. Cadmium forms two mixed complex species, $[\text{Cd}(\text{OX})_2(\text{SCN})]^{2-}$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{OX})(\text{SCN})_2]^{2-}$ with their respective stability constants : $\log \beta_{21} = 4.80$ and $\log \beta_{12} = 3.90$. The absence of $[\text{Cd}(\text{OX})(\text{SCN})]^-$ complex species is indicated by the negative value of β_{11} . It is observed that the mixed ligand complexes have higher stabilities than would be predicted on statistical considerations. The observed enhancements of the complexation constants of the mixed complex species were attributed to the possibilities of i) some extra weak bonding between unlike bound ligands, ii) the gross statistical effect and iii) electrostatic effects.

IN the past few years a detailed study of mixed complexes has been made by potentiometric¹ and spectrophotometric² techniques. However, in recent years, the polarographic technique is also receiving considerable attention in this field after the work of Schaap and McMasters³. Mixed ligand complexes of cadmium with oxalate and salicylate ions were investigated polarographically in this laboratory⁴. The enhancements in the stabilities of Cd(II)-oxalate-salicylate mixed complexes were interpreted in terms of the possibility of simultaneous π -bonding between the metal ions and the ligands and the electrostatic effect. Cd(II)-oxalate-thiocyanate system was chosen with a view to study the nature of mixed ligand complexes wherein the second ligand is not an organic acid as taken earlier⁴ but is an ambient anion.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of reagent grade. Complexing agents were used in the form of their potassium salts. Potassium nitrate was used to maintain an ionic strength constant at 1.0M. All solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water.

Half-wave potentials and diffusion currents were measured on a Cambridge Pen Recording type polarograph. Before recording the polarograms purified nitrogen was bubbled through the experimental solution to remove the dissolved oxygen. The dropping mercury electrode had the following characteristics :

$$t = 3.0 \text{ sec in } 0.1M \text{ KNO}_3 \text{ (open circuit)}$$
$$m = 1.97 \text{ mg sec}^{-1}.$$

The measurements were made in an air conditioned room where the temperature was maintained at $25^\circ \pm 5^\circ$. All the potential measurements were made against a saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.) which had negligible cell resistance. The half-wave potential values were obtained from log plots.

Results and Discussion

Simple systems of Cd(II)-oxalate and Cd(II)-thiocyanate were investigated polarographically in order to obtain their stabilities under identical experimental conditions maintained for Cd(II)-oxalate-thiocyanate mixed system. Wherever possible the values of the stabilities and of the constants in mixed systems were also obtained by the method of least squares and are given in brackets.

The stability constants of Cd(II)-oxalate system :
In each solution the concentration of Cd^{2+} was maintained constant at 1mM and the oxalate[OX] concentrations were varied from 0.02 to 0.50M. The relationship between $-(E_{1/2})_c$ and $\log C_L$ (where C_L = oxalate concentration) reveals the existence of $[\text{Cd}(\text{OX})]$, $[\text{Cd}(\text{OX})_2]^{2-}$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{OX})_4]^{4-}$ species with their respective stability constants : $\log \beta_{10} = 2.70 \pm 0.04$, $\log \beta_{20} = 4.07 \pm 0.15$ and $\log \beta_{30} = 5.14 \pm 0.06$. These values agreed well with those obtained by Schaap and McMasters³, Kanemura and Watters⁵ and Kaden et al⁶.
(4.08) (5.14)

taking into consideration the difference in experimental conditions.

Stability constants of Cd(II)-thiocyanate system :
In every solution, Cd^{2+} concentration was 1mM. The concentration of potassium thiocyanate[SCN] varied from 0.10 to 1.0M. DeFord and Hume⁷ treatment of the data revealed the existence of four complexes $[\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})]^+$, $[\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_2]$, $[\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_3]^-$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{SCN})_4]^{2-}$ with their respective stability constants : $\log \beta_{01} = 1.04 \pm 0.04$, $\log \beta_{02} = 1.74 \pm 0.03$, $\log \beta_{03} = 1.00 \pm 0.02$ and $\log \beta_{04} = 1.90 \pm 0.01$. These values are in reasonable agreement with those obtained by Humffray et al.⁸ and Dhoot and Karmalkar⁹. The thiocyanate ion possesses two different donor atoms viz. the softer 'S' preferred by soft acids such as Cd^{2+} , Cu^+ , Ag^+ , etc. and the harder 'N' preferred by hard

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acids such as Fe^{3+} , Co^{3+} , UO_2^{2+} , etc.¹⁰. It can, therefore, be inferred that cadmium thiocyanate binding occurs through S. There is no ligand field stabilization in the Cd^{2+} ion because of its completed 'd' shells. Thus the stereochemistry of its compounds is determined solely by considerations of size, electrostatic forces and covalent bonding forces.

The Cd(II)-oxalate-thiocyanate mixed system: The thiocyanate ion concentrations were kept constant at 0.1 M and 0.40M because at these concentrations 1:1 and 1:2 Cd(II)-thiocyanate complexes respectively were found to be predominant species. In the mixed ligand system, two sets of experiments were carried out. In the first set, the neutral solutions containing 1mM Cd^{2+} , 0.16M thiocyanate ions were polarographed at varying concentrations of oxalate ions. Ionic

strength was maintained at 1.0M. The same procedure was repeated in the second set wherein thiocyanate concentration was kept constant at 0.40M.

In all the above sets, the slope values of the log plots were in the range of 30 to 33 mV which indicated reversible reduction involving two electrons. The linear relationship of diffusion current and square root of effective height of mercury head in every case indicated the diffusion controlled nature of the system. The experimental data of $-(E_{1/2})_e$, F_{10} functions and slope values are set out in Tables 1 and 2. The shift to a more negative value in half-wave potential of Cd^{2+} in the presence of thiocyanate and oxalate ions is greater than that of in oxalate ions alone. This proves the formation of Cd(II)-oxalate-thiocyanate mixed complexes.

TABLE 1— F_{10} as function of [OX]

C_L [OX] M	$\text{Cd}^{2+}=1\text{mM}$ [SCN] = 0.16M		$\log I_m$ I_c	Slope (mV)	$\mu=1.0\text{M}(\text{KNO}_3)$ $-(E_{1/2})_e = 0.538\text{V}$, Temp. = $25^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$			
	$-E_{1/2}$ vs S. C. E. at 0.00M [SCN]	at 0.16M [SCN]			$F_{00} \times 10^{-5}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-5}$	$F_{20} \times 10^{-5}$	$F_{30} \times 10^{-5}$
0.02	0.618	0.631	0.0196	30.8	0.031	0.590	—	—
0.04	0.633	0.642	0.0350	32.0	0.096	1.924	—	—
0.06	0.643	0.651	0.0374	32.6	0.161	1.770	—	—
0.08	0.649	0.657	0.0350	32.6	0.242	2.780	—	—
0.10	0.654	0.664	0.0350	32.8	0.448	4.287	3.800	0.00
0.15	0.667	0.673	0.0350	30.6	0.912	5.949	3.690	0.993
0.20	0.678	0.682	0.0457	31.0	1.922	9.510	4.550	1.175
0.30	0.690	0.694	0.0512	31.4	4.864	16.146	5.248	1.016
0.40	0.700	0.705	0.0566	32.6	11.270	28.125	6.931	1.182
0.50	0.708	0.712	0.0566	30.2	20.410	40.780	8.076	1.175

log A = 1.30, log B = 2.60 ± 0.01 , log C = 4.34 ± 0.03 and log D = 5.04 ± 0.08
(4.42) (5.00)

TABLE 2— F_{10} as function of [OX]

C_L [OX] M	$\text{Cd}^{2+}=1\text{mM}$ [SCN] = 0.40M		$\log I_m$ I_c	Slope (mV)	$\mu=1.0\text{M}(\text{KNO}_3)$ $-(E_{1/2})_e = 0.589\text{V}$, Temp. = $25^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$			
	$-E_{1/2}$ vs S. C. E. at 0.00M [SCN]	at 0.40M [SCN]			$F_{00} \times 10^{-5}$	$F_{10} \times 10^{-5}$	$F_{20} \times 10^{-5}$	$F_{30} \times 10^{-5}$
0.02	0.618	0.646	0.0196	29.6	0.089	1.962	—	—
0.04	0.633	0.653	0.0298	28.0	0.165	2.880	—	—
0.06	0.643	0.659	0.0512	32.0	0.272	3.705	—	—
0.08	0.649	0.667	0.0402	31.0	0.527	5.978	—	—
0.10	0.654	0.669	0.0512	32.0	0.599	5.498	4.498	—
0.15	0.667	0.680	0.0618	32.0	1.524	9.826	5.884	1.450
0.20	0.678	0.689	0.0566	32.0	2.900	14.250	6.625	1.460
0.30	0.690	0.700	0.0674	32.0	7.375	24.416	7.805	1.368
0.40	0.700	0.708	0.0792	31.6	14.450	36.000	8.750	1.262
0.50	0.708	0.715	0.0792	31.0	25.370	50.640	9.928	1.245

Log A = 1.70, log B = 3.00 ± 0.02 , log C = 4.57 ± 0.03 and log D = 5.11 ± 0.06
(4.57) (5.18)

The values of constant A, B, C and D in both the sets were evaluated with the help of the method of Schaap and McMasters⁸. These are presented below :

At 0.16M [SCN] : log A=1.30, log B=2.60 ± 0.01,
log C=4.34 ± 0.03, log D=5.04 ± 0.08
(4.42) (5.00)

At 0.40M [SCN] : log A=1.70, log B=3.00 ± 0.02,
log C=4.57 ± 0.03, log D=5.12 ± 0.06
(4.57) (5.18)

The log $\beta_{30} = 5.14 \pm 0.06$, which agrees well with the mean value of log D = 5.08. The values given in brackets are obtained by the method of least squares.

The stability constants of mixed species were calculated from these constants. These are : log $\beta_{21} = 4.10$ and log $\beta_{12} = 3.90$. The negative value of β_{11}^{-1} indicates the absence of 1:1 i. e. $[\text{Cd}(\text{OX})(\text{SCN})]^{-}$ complex species in the solution.

The determination of composition and the calculation of their stability constants of mixed complexes show that in the thiocyanate complex of cadmium the replacement of thiocyanate by oxalate takes place as was confirmed by the nature of the functions F_{40} . This is confirmed by the fact that the mean value of coefficient D coincides exactly with the stability constant β_{30} for $[\text{Cd}(\text{OX})_3]^{4-}$ complex (log $\beta_{30} = 5.14$ and mean log D = 5.08).

Watters et al.¹¹ have proposed the procedure to predict the complexation constants. The predicted value for complexation constant for $[\text{Cd}(\text{OX})_2(\text{SCN})]^{3-}$ was $3 \times \beta_{20}^{2/3} \times \beta_{03}^{1/3} = 10^{3.63}$ while the observed value was $10^{4.80}$. Thus the enhancement was $10^{+1.27}$. For the mixed complex species $[\text{Cd}(\text{OX})(\text{SCN})_2]^{2-}$ the complexation constant was $3 \times \beta_{10}^{1/3} \times \beta_{02}^{2/3} = 10^{3.33}$ as compared to $10^{3.90}$ observed with the enhancement of $10^{+0.57}$.

It is observed that enhancement is more for $[\text{Cd}(\text{OX})_2(\text{SCN})]^{3-}$ than for $[\text{Cd}(\text{OX})(\text{SCN})_2]^{2-}$. This enhancements may be due to cooperative effects of electrostatic forces between different kinds of ligands and steric effects.

The various complexation reactions with their log stability constants may be represented as :

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References

1. E. G. SASE and D. V. JAHAGIRDAR, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, 37, 985.
2. M. TANAKA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, 36, 151.
3. W. B. SCHAAP and D. L. MCMASTERS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4699.
4. D. G. DHULEY, D. V. JAHAGIRDAR and D. D. KHANOLKAR, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, (in press).
5. Y. KANEMURA and J. I. WATTERS, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, 29, 1701.
6. TH. KADEN and S. FALLAB, *Chimia (Switz.)*, 1966, 20, 51.
7. D. D. DEFORD and D. N. HUME, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 5321.
8. A. A. HUMFFARY, A. M. BOND and J. S. FORREST, *J. Electroanalyt. Chem.*, 1967, 15, 67.
9. L. N. DHOOT and P. K. KARMALKAR, *Vikram Univ. J.*, 1960, 4, 81.
10. R. G. PEARSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 3533.
11. J. I. WATTERS and R. DEWITT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 1333.